

Reconfigurable Metasurface Antennas based on Varactor Diodes

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Abstract—Radiation control of modulated metasurface antennas by means of tunable capacitances is studied in this work. Two reconfigurable topologies are presented, each of them performs beam-scanning controlled by the bias voltage of varactor diodes. The study commences from a single-layer metasurface antenna whose modulation period is actively changed, being extended to a double-layer design with scan angle dictated by a single parameter. Numerical results are reported, demonstrating the versatile control of the leaky-wave aperture field, as well as the good performance in terms of beam shape and field of view.

Index Terms—Reconfigurable antennas, metasurfaces, leaky-wave antenna (LWA), electromagnetic bandgap structures (EBG), periodic surfaces.

I. INTRODUCTION

Current and future communication networks are demanding real-time control of the reflection and scattering of radio waves through the propagation medium. The concept of a new controllable scenario, whose aim is to unlock new limits in terms of performance metrics, has encouraged research on the existing theoretical frameworks for channel characterization. New communication models account for the several states of an active channel, due to this generalization, the interaction with the environment is taking the shape of an optimization problem, which at the physical layer implies the design of electromagnetic devices able to follow the specifications of the new paradigm.

From the transmitter point of view, reconfigurable antennas based on tunable materials or integrated electronic devices are strong candidates to survive this evolution of communication networks. Because of the reconfigurability speed, beam-scanning based on switching elements can be the starting point that provides continuous connectivity in a multi-user environment. The last feature, together with its consequent reduction of interference, leads to an improved spectral efficiency of the channel while a keeping high quality of service (QoS). Furthermore, the energy efficiency of the system is increased at the same time.

When it comes to address the previous issue, periodic leaky-wave antennas can play a vital role. They present low-complexity feeding, high-directivity and scanning capability controlled through the phase velocity of the guided waves. These inherent features, together with a simple low-profile integration, propose them as promising solutions to be implemented in novel telecommunications systems.

More specifically, leaky-wave phenomenology based on the metasurface concept, where a periodic impedance boundary condition is implemented by electrically small unit cells, creates advantages when it comes to control the aperture field. In this case, not only the propagation phase can be adjusted, but also the amplitude of the aperture field can be flexibly controlled, thanks to the implemented small lattice.

As previously stated, antenna design based on integrated electronic devices opens a world of possibilities. First preliminary studies on electronically scannable leaky-wave antennas were reported in [1], where the inclusion of switching elements in reconfigurable dielectric waveguides was theorized. In 2000, a pioneer design based on PIN diodes was proposed [2]. This investigation proposed a dielectric waveguide loaded with metal strips. By switching the grating spacing between two states using PIN diodes, electronic scanning was achieved for a couple of discrete angles. Moreover, the progressive phasing control of travelling wave antennas through tunable capacitances was studied in [3]. Here, varactors were first implemented on the same layer as the microstrip antenna. In [4], electronic steering of a reflected beam was achieved by loading varactors on a high-impedance surface. Years later, the problem was translated to leaky-wave Fabry-Perot antennas to electronically scan the beam [5].

The past decade has seen the inclusion of reconfigurability in metasurface antennas. A set of novel implementations for current wireless networks can be found in [6]. Recently, [7] and [8] have proposed the use of the metasurface approach to achieve flexible reconfigurable scanning. The reported design proves the effectiveness of a scanning mechanism based on the electronic definition of a periodic impedance boundary condition (IBC) through PIN diodes. This approach allows for the flexible control of the modulation period of the structure, thus, providing a wide scanning range.

This study aims to contribute to this growing area with a metasurface based solution that properly reconfigures the IBCs, so as to control the aperture field in terms of amplitude and phase. By adding tunable capacitances (varactor diodes) in the unit cell, the pointing direction can be controlled, as well as the leakage, extending the capabilities of technique [7]. As a result, fast beam-hopping with enhanced freedom in terms of beamwidth is achieved. Moreover, a second topology that provides an innovative solution in terms of control simplicity is presented. The following sections attempt to show a compar-

ison between both, focusing on how these topologies expand the performance limits of modulated metasurface antennas.

II. DESIGN METHODOLOGY

Radiation in uniform leaky-wave antennas comes from the fundamental mode of a wave-guiding structure. Due to the boundary conditions of the problem, they are generally dispersive and the consequent transverse resonance forces the excited waves to be fast, so that a radiation angle is consequently defined. Our proposed structures, instead, support slow (or surface) waves. Therefore, they radiate only in the presence of a proper periodic modulation. Fig. 1 shows the permitted values of the propagation constant for an unmodulated metasurface, whose unit cell is reported in Fig. 2. This latter consists of a metal cavity, which is dielectric filled, with a square slot etched on the upper wall and a central via. A tunable capacitance is connected across the slot and used to introduce a periodic modulation. Due to the small electrical size of the unit cell, BCs can be homogenized by associating a reactance value X_s to any specific configuration. Such impedances univocally define how bounded are the waves to the surface. The presented methodology exploits the previous concept to obtain leaky-wave radiation by using small tunable elements.

Fig. 1. TM surface wave dispersion of the unloaded unit cell.

The fundamental cell behaves equivalently as a resonant circuit with small capacitances on top, which are defined by the gap between the patch and the surrounding metal. For a certain frequency, by placing varactor diodes in the slot, it is possible to change the equivalent homogenized impedance, getting a set of solutions for the resonance equation:

$$\eta_0 \frac{k_z}{k_0} - jX_s(C_v) = 0 \quad (1)$$

Where k_0 and k_z the free space and transverse wavenumber, respectively, η_0 is the free space impedance and $X_s(C_v)$ the homogenized surface reactance, which is a function of the tuned capacitance. As each solution has an associated surface wave velocity, we end up having a set of surfaces with different homogenized impedance (Fig. 3).

$$X_s(C_v) = \eta_0 \sqrt{\frac{k_{x_0}^2(C_v)}{k_0^2} - 1} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 2. Unit cell of the metasurface presented in Section III.

Fig. 3. Resonance tuning for a uniform metasurface.

Since the lattice is small compared to the period and the considered variation smooth, we can use the previous solutions to model the structure through a continuous variation of the impedance, which leads to a periodical modulation of the amplitude function of the electric and magnetic fields. Such a simple perturbation allows to describe them in terms of an infinite set of spatial harmonics, whose transverse propagation constant is given by:

$$k_{z_n} = \sqrt{k_0^2 - \left(k_{x_0} + \frac{2\pi n}{d}\right)^2}; \forall n \in \mathbb{Z} \quad (3)$$

Where k_{z_n} is the transverse wavenumber of the n th Floquet harmonic, k_{x_0} is the propagation constant of the zero mode, n is the harmonic order and d the modulation period. It follows from (3) that, when condition (4) holds,

$$d > \frac{2\pi}{k_{x_0} - k_0} \quad (4)$$

transverse resonance occurs and the solution of k_{z_n} becomes real for the $n = -1$ mode. Therefore, the latter field harmonic becomes fast ($k_{x_{-1}} < k_0$) and a radiation angle (θ_{Rad}) is defined.

$$\sin(\theta_{Rad}^{n=-1}) = \frac{k_0 \sqrt{1 + X_s'^2} - \frac{2\pi}{d}}{k_0} \quad (5)$$

III. MULTIPLE CONTROL DESIGN: SCANNING CONTROLLED BY THE PERIODICITY

The scanning mechanism of the present topology is based on the period reconfiguration of the modulated impedance. By reducing or enlarging the periodicity (d), the propagation constant of the $n = -1$ harmonic is decreased or increased, respectively, thus making it possible to steer the beam at a constant frequency. If d is big enough, the longitudinal wavenumber of other higher-order harmonics falls in the visible region and the far field pattern presents grating lobes.

The reason why this technique brings freedom to set the modulation depth is related to the resonant nature of the unit cell. As a result of it, the elements of the metasurface are constantly tuned in the vicinity of the unloaded structure bandgap. As Fig. 3 represents, it is possible to hit the resonance of the cells by raising the tunable capacitance (C_v), thus forbidding wave propagation. In this region, a small capacitance growth strongly slows down the surface waves. Because of it, the range of operation of a commercial varactor is enough to define the impedance dynamic needed to significantly excite the $n = -1$ harmonic (Fig. 4). The closer the design is to the resonance, the more phase variation and the greater is the control over the leakage.

Fig. 4. (a) Database for the implementation of the IBC. (b) Recreation of the IBC through pixels.

Through the database plotted in Fig. 4a, we can choose the capacitance of the varactors so that the surface impedance follows a sinusoidal modulation with a desired depth, and a period such that the $n = -1$ acquires a certain phase velocity.

$$d = \frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{1 + X_s'^2} - \sin(\theta_{Rad})} \quad (6)$$

Where θ_{Rad} is the desired pointing angle and X_s' the normalized average impedance, which also affects the leakage.

Fig. 5 shows how the reconfiguration of the period by virtue of varactor diodes allows for beam-hopping, making the design compatible with the latest communications technologies.

Fig. 5. Scanning pattern of the single-layer design.

IV. SINGLE CONTROL DESIGN: SCANNING THROUGH THE AVERAGE IMPEDANCE

Whereas the structure introduced in Section III needs a bias line with multiple voltage controls, since the tuning of the varactors follows itself the continuous impedance boundary. The present two-layer topology allows for a single parameter control network.

The design is composed by a variable capacitive surface on top of a dielectric, which is loaded in the bottom by the periodic circuit whose unit cell is presented in Fig. 2. The top layer is responsible for the radiation because it adds a periodic modulation to the underlying IBC. Beam-scanning is obtained by uniformly changing the impedance of the unmodulated bottom boundary, where all the varactors are reconfigured with equal capacitances C_v , as Fig. 6 illustrates. In this way, the phase propagation of the surface wave can be accurately controlled. The gap between the lateral walls of the cell and central patch defines a capacitance, in addition, an inductance is associated to the grounded pin. Both quantities can be adjusted in order to optimize the dispersive behavior of our structure at $f = 20$ GHz, letting us perform beam-scanning within a desired range of capacitances C_v .

Fig. 6. Conceptual model of the proposed two-layer metasurface antenna.

As previously described, the stepped phase response is a consequence of working near the bandgap of the periodic structure. This explains why the tuning of the bottom layer modifies the transverse wavenumber of the slow mode running

over the fixed periodicity, thus allowing for beam-hopping based on a unique parameter (Fig. 6). Therefore, the final outcome is the reconfiguration of the guided wavelength (λ_{sw}).

Fig. 7. Unit cell of the single control antenna.

Fig. 8. (a) Family of dispersion curves for the different bottom layer impedances. (b) Dispersion characteristic of the top elements.

The static capacitance modulation of the upper layer is implemented through the variation of the geometrical parameter R_e , the main dimension of the top element. Fig. 8b represents how the elements modulate the impedance around an average value set by the varactors. Hence, it is the top modulation the responsible of creating the periodic impedance variation that excites the $n = -1$ Floquet harmonic.

Fig. 9. Scanning pattern of the single control structure.

Fig. 9 illustrates how the radiated beam is scanned when the lower metasurface is uniformly tuned, consequently achieving reconfigurability controlled by one parameter.

V. CONCLUSION

Comparing the two topologies, it can be seen that the design reported in Section III presents, in principle, no field of view limitation. However, when scanning in the forward quadrant, the $n = -2$ Floquet wave becomes fast and a secondary lobe appears. Despite this, the dispersion never bounds the scanning, since the group velocity remains unchanged among all the configurations. In contrast, Fig. 8b reports the decline of the group velocity in the two-layer metasurface, which occurs as C_v increases. This implies a reduced operational bandwidth. Furthermore, this configuration also presents limited scanning range, due to the narrow set of achievable propagation constant values. This is depicted by Fig. 10 and Fig. 11. As the bandgap is closer (for higher capacitances C_v), the fixed physical modulation on top influences more the wave velocity, resulting in a stronger leakage defined by a high impedance boundary condition.

Fig. 10. Tuning effect on the IBC in the two-layer metasurface.

As observed in Fig. 10, small capacitance variations through R_e imply bigger changes on the surface impedance, leading to higher leakage rates. This is represented in Fig.11 by the S_{21} parameter. Results show that scanning based on the average impedance cannot keep a stable aperture illumination for all the configurations. On the other hand, it brings a simple solution in terms of control complexity, which is one of the challenging issues when it comes to design reconfigurable antennas.

Fig. 11. (a) Scattering parameters of the single-layer design. (b) Scattering parameters of the two-layer design.

In summary, this study shows that radiation control of modulated metasurface antennas based on tunable capacitances allows to control the degrees of freedom of

future wireless channels. Thus, proposing them as powerful solutions for communication systems where throughput and low-latency localization are flexibly customized in real-time.

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